

Stress Management and Coping Strategies in the Banking Industry (A Comparative Study on Managerial Cadre of Public and Private Sector Banks)

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Abstract

Job stress has adverse effects on both organizations and employees. Previous studies examining the causes of job stress paid little attention to stress management and coping strategies, especially in the banking sector. The nature of work of bankers and family life may most often expose them to high level of stress which has the potential of affecting their productive capacity. Data for the study were collected from the field using interview schedules and questionnaires. The descriptive statistical, t-test statistical technique in testing the relationship among variables. Findings from the study show the existence of high level of stress among the Bankers. An attempt has been made to find out the association between the female and male coping mechanisms during stress. The nature of work of bankers and family life may most often expose them to high level of stress which has the potential of affecting their productive capacity. This study therefore sought to find out the stress and coping strategies of bankers in Tema. This study adopted a mixed method to investigate the nature of stress and the coping strategies adopted by Bankers in the Tema Metropolis. Data for the study were collected from the field using interview schedules and questionnaires. Findings from the study show the existence of high level of stress among the Bankers. The sources of stress among the bankers range from the upbringing of their children, their families to the nature of their work. In terms of coping strategies of stress, it was revealed that the respondents indulge in religious activities, exercises, share with friends, use medicinal therapies, counseling and social

gathering. The need for appropriate mechanisms to be put in place by the managements of the banks to address the counseling needs of employees is indicated by the findings. Also, organization of seminars for employees to help broaden their minds on stress coping strategies as well as to keep them abreast with the changing trend of issues is very essential to help reduce their stress levels. The nature of work of bankers and family life may most often expose them to high level of stress which has the potential of affecting their productive capacity. This study therefore sought to find out the stress and coping strategies of bankers in Tema. This study adopted a mixed method to investigate the nature of stress and the coping strategies adopted by Bankers in the Tema Metropolis. Data for the study were collected from the field using interview schedules and questionnaires. Findings from the study show the existence of high level of stress among the Bankers. The sources of stress among the bankers range from the upbringing of their children, their families to the nature of their work. In terms of coping strategies of stress, it was revealed that the respondents indulge in religious activities, exercises, share with friends, use medicinal therapies, counseling and social gathering. The need for appropriate mechanisms to be put in place by the managements of the banks to address the counseling needs of employees is indicated by the findings. Also, organization of seminars for employees to help broaden their minds on stress coping strategies as well as to keep them abreast with the changing trend of issues is very essential to help reduce their stress levels.

Keywords:- Coping strategies, Stress management, public & private sector banks.

Introduction: -

Several crises have engulfed societies in the world at this time and age along with most employees having a hard time to cope with the stress in the work place (World Health Organization (WHO), 2005). Stress has become a pervading issue of everyone's life in this modern world. The modern world which is often regarded as a

world of achievements has become a world of stress. Be it family, any social activity or any business organization, stress is everywhere. Stress is a body's way to react to a challenge. It is a state of psychological and/ or physiological imbalance resulting from the disparity between situational demand and the individual's ability and/ or motivation to meet those demands. Dr. Hans

Selye, who has been one of the leading authorities on the concept of stress, has described it as “the rate of all wear and tear caused by life.” Stress may be positive or negative. It can be positive when the situation offers an opportunity for a person to gain something. It acts as a motivator for peak performance. On the other hand, it can be negative when a person faces social, physical, organizational and emotional problems. Various studies have depicted that stress is increasing at a rising rate in the Banking sector. Due to recession in the global market and cut-throat competition, banks are facing many challenges. Nowadays, employees at workplace experience a lot of stress due to deadlines, excessive work load, job insecurities, career uncertainties, longer working hours, reduced autonomy and increased responsibility. Not only these, the inculcation of the instinct, through various cultural practices, to emerge as a winner in every situation also stresses up the individual. Needless to say, this stress not only adversely affects the professional and physical efficiency of the individual to fulfil the overall demands of the workplace and of the personal and family life, but also creates varied health problems. The advent of technological revolution in all walks of life coupled with globalisation, privatisation policies has drastically changed conventional patterns in all sectors. The banking sector is of no exemption. The 1990s saw radical policy changes with regarding to fiscal deficit and structural changes in India so as to prepare to cope with the new economic world order. Globalisation and privatisation led policies compelled the banking sector to reform and adjust to have a competitive edge to cope with multinationals led environment. The advent of technological changes, especially extensive use of computers in the banking sector has changed the work patterns of the bank employees and has made it inevitable to downsize the work force in the sector (Bakker et al., 2005). There are three basic reasons why stress and coping with stress in organizations are becoming prominent topics of research and organizational practices. First, Health/Well-being: Employees are treated as an asset to the organization. Therefore, an employee’s health is important to the individual employee, organization and society. A variety of the health hazards associated with stress in organizations (Van et al., 2005). Physical hazards that may

occur because of occupational stress include fatigue, headache, stomach problems, muscles aches and pains, chronic mild illness, sleep disturbances and eating disorders. Psychological and behavioral problems that may develop include anxiety, irritability, alcohol and drug use, feeling powerless and low morale. If exposure to stressors in the workplace is prolonged then chronic health problems can occur including cardiovascular diseases like stroke, high blood pressure and immune system dysfunction (Beehr & Newman, 1978; Reddy, & Yusuf, 1998).

Review Of Literature: -

Abdulla et al., (2016) conducted a study on “Stress Coping Strategies: An Experiential Exploration Of Bank Executives” to identify individual coping strategies (effective and ineffective) used by the bank Executives to enact stress, to identify the coping dispositions employed by the organisation to reduce stress among the employees/Executives and to suggest workable stress reduction strategies which Executives/ organisation could use to lower stress levels in the banking sector. The study covered a sample of around 159 Executives/ respondents selected through stratified random sampling from J&K bank. The sample consisted of scale I/Associate Executives, scale II/Executives, Scale III/Senior Executives and scale IV/Executive Manager working at different hierarchical levels at different places across J&K. It had been observed that executives used more of problem focused coping strategies than that of non-problem focused coping strategies to cope with stress, except in case of avoiding confrontation with others which is an avoidance strategy.

Executives tended to use problem focused copings along with emotional focused copings in the organisation. In case of organizational intervention to deal with stress they perceived providing benefits in the form of incentives for efficient work as the best organizational strategy. They perceived the effective and performance appraisal as the best tool of the organisation to deal with stress affecting its executives. They equally supported participation of executives in the decision making followed by family welfare schemes for the employees by the organisation.

Sharma, (2016) studied “Stress and Coping with Stress: A Comparative Study of Male and Female Teachers in Universities”. The

objective of the study was to examine the level of stress among university teachers and compare it on the basis of gender and to study the various coping strategies used by teachers to cope up with the stress at job. For the purpose of the study, the primary data was collected by using questionnaires: academic stress and coping strategies questionnaire. The consisted the sample of 120 teachers randomly chosen from two universities, namely, Guru Nanak Dev University and Punjabi University, Patiala 60 male and 60 female teachers. The statistical tools used were frequencies, percentages, averages, mean per statement, standard deviation, ranking, chi square, mean percentage, t-test, correlation and regression analysis.

The results of the study stated that majority of respondents 73.33% respondents fall in the medium stress category number of female respondents was lower than males in this category but in case of highly stressed number of females were more than male respondents. The results stated that only in case of administrative and government the mean stress score (per statement) of female teachers was significantly higher than male teachers. For the factors, students and colleagues females' mean was higher than males but difference was significant at least level of significance. For the factor family there was no significant difference in the mean score of females and males. The mean score in case of society and job was higher in case of males than females but the difference was not significant. The overall mean score of stress caused by all the factors was slightly higher among females than males but the difference was non-significant.

Shah, (2012) investigated in "Management of Job Stress: An Empirical Analysis" the management of job stress in banking industry. The objectives of the study were to analyse whether there existed stress in the banking industry or not, to underline the nature and type of stress associated with the banking industry, to find out the forces for stimulating stress and to suggest the measures for overcoming the stress. The sample of the study consisted respondents in different banks in Kashmir Division namely, The Jammu and Kashmir Bank Ltd., (J&K), The Punjab National Bank (PNB) and The State Bank of India (SBI). About 58 samples respondents were chosen for the study purposes comprising, 34% (20) high level officers, 43% (25) medium level officers and

22% (13) lower level officer's significance. Considering the nature and the job specification, it has been significantly observed that banking industry is overwhelming exposed to a serious amount of stress. However, the extent of stress varies among members within the banking industry.

Goyal & Mehta, (2011) conducted their research "Organisational Role Stress among Call Centre Employees" on call centre employees of NCR-Delhi region representing North India hub and Mohali representing Punjab hub. Ten call centres each from Mohali and NCR Delhi regions were selected and five employees each from call centre were selected on the basis of willingness to respond. Thus the sample size was 100 respondents from 20 call centers that call centre employees remained under tremendous stress. The research revealed that all ten types of role stressors are the key stresses in the case of these employees. Personal inadequacy, role isolation and role ambiguity affect the maximum number of employees.

Level of stress for personal inadequacy, resource inadequacy, role ambiguity, inter-role distance, self-role distance and role overload is higher in NCR-Delhi region, while role stagnation, role isolation, role erosion are up to higher level in Mohali. To relieve these employees of various types of role stresses work load per employee should be reduced. Career planning should be done; training should be provided to the employees; and the customers should also be educated about talking to call centre employees in a nice manner.

Objectives Of The Study:-

1. To test the impact of stressors like job factors, organizational factors and family factors on the health of the managerial cadre in the banking organizations.
2. To assess the level of job stress among the managers in the banking industry.

Hypotheses Of The Study:-

Ha1: There is a significant difference in the level of stress among male and female cadres of the select banking organizations.

Ha2: Coping strategies have a significant impact on the health of the managerial cadre in the banking organizations.

Methodology:-

The study is mainly based upon primary data which were collected from employees of the 02

bank branches through structured questionnaires. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the sampling units for the study. Three main stages were involved in the sampling selection: Banks, Branches and individual respondents. First, the banks were stratified into two: public banks and foreign banks. Two banks were selected from each stratum purposively. The quantitative data collected from the field were edited, coded, and analysed using SPSS version 22.0.

Sample And Sample Size:-

The total universe (managerial cadre) of the select public and private sector banking organizations in the Ujjain district of Madhya Pradesh. To conduct this study 02 bank branches from two categories of banks have been selected as representative sample units. Out of the 80 employees selected 45 were male employees while 35 were female employees. The select banking organizations

are 01 organization from the public sector and 01 organization from the private sector. The public sector banking organizations selected for the study is State Bank of India, The private sector banking organizations selected for the study is Axis bank. . Hence the sample size from public sector banking organizations is 50 and that of private sector banking organizations is 30 and the total sample size fixed for the research study is 80.

Statistical Tool:-

In order to collect the data through survey following self- developed and standardized tools has been used: Job and Organizational Factor Scale (5- point Likert scale) Negative Affectivity (Fortunato and Goldblad 2002) (7- point Likert scale) Organizational stress scale (5- point Likert scale) and Stress symptoms management strategies scale(5- point Likert scale)

Analysis and Interpretation:-

Table No. 01 , Stress among Male and Female Public Sector Bank Managers

Org. Stress Variables	Male Public Sector Bank Managers N=45		Female Public Sector Bank Managers N=35		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
POSC (S1)	28.64	2.05	22.25	1.87	14.3663	0.0001
PIR (S2)	16,54	1.22	16.42	1.48	0.3975	0.6921
WO (S3)	12,66	1.02	12.48	1.43	0.6569	0.5132
WI (S4)	14.65	1.29	14.49	2.02	0.4307	0.6679
TP (S5)	11.28	1.18	11.15	1.27	0.4728	0.6377
FN&JI (S6)	18.32	1.20	18.20	2.36	0.2958	0.7682
IS (S7)	13.18	1.10	12.68	1.96	1.4450	0.1525
RR (S8)	14.24	1.02	14.12	1.09	0.6754	0.5014
RA (S9)	15.27	1.31	15.17	1.65	0.3023	0.7633
MJ (S10)	16.83	1.44	17.12	1.59	0.8537	0.3959
TOTAL	161.61	12.83	154.08	16.72	2.2801	0.0253

The female public sector bank managers were more suffered with the problem of no freedom of expression, inconsistent and unrealistic management attitude, non-participative decision making, restricted flow of communication, organisational politics, non- recognition of good

performance, frequent changes in policies and procedures and stagnant organisation as compare to the male public sector bank managers. Thus the results clearly indicated that the male bank managers were more suffered with the problem of monotonous job as compare to female public sector bank

managers. The t- test had been applied which indicated that there was a significant difference in the total stress levels suffered by female and male public sector bank managers. The results of t- test clearly indicated that that the difference in stress

levels was significant in the total stress level and in case of individual organizational stress variables the difference was significant only for one factor out of ten factors that was poor organizational structure and climate S1.

Table No. 02 , Stress among Male and Female Bank Managers in Private Sector

Org. Stress Variables	Male Private Sector Bank Managers N=45		Female Private Sector Bank Managers N=35		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
POSC (S1)	22.42	2.31	21.72	2.10	1.3985	0.1659
PIR (S2)	13.69	1.58	13.47	1.73	0.5927	0.5551
WO (S3)	18.28	1.02	18.20	1.98	0.2343	0.8154
WI (S4)	21.36	1.21	21.18	2.30	0.4513	0.6530
TP (S5)	19.55	1.42	19.43	1.58	0.3569	0.7221
FN&JI (S6)	20.18	1.14	20.02	2.39	0.3954	0.6936
IS (S7)	17.65	1.06	17.05	2.14	1.6416	0.1047
RR (S8)	15.77	1.09	15.64	1.18	0.1300	0.6112
RA (S9)	16.86	1.31	16.78	1.66	0.2410	0.8102
MJ (S10)	17.24	1.52	17.49	1.70	0.6929	0.4904
TOTAL	183.00	13.66	180.98	18.76	0.5573	0.5789

The female private sector bank managers were more suffered with the problem of no freedom of expression, inconsistent and unrealistic management attitude, non-participative decision making, restricted flow of communication, organisational politics, non- recognition of good performance, frequent changes in policies and procedures and stagnant organisation as compare to the male private sector bank managers. Thus the results clearly indicated that the male bank managers were more suffered with the problem of

monotonous job as compare to female private sector bank managers.

The t- test had been applied which indicated that stress suffered by female private sector bank managers was more but the difference in stress levels was not significant at any level. The results of t-test clearly indicated that that the difference in stress levels was insignificant in the total stress level and in case of individual organizational stress variables the difference was also not significant for any factor out of ten factors.

Table No.03 Coping Strategies among Bank Managers

Coping Strategies	Public Sector Bank N=50		Private Sector Bank N=30		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Escape/Avoidance (E/A) (C1)	16.85	1.34	20.34	1.81	9.8664	0.0001
Positive Thinking (PT) (C2)	21.11	1.28	21.29	1.22	0.6196	0.5374
Problem Solving (PS) (C3)	17.45	1.67	18.92	1.51	3.9478	0.0002
Social Support (SS) (C4)	12.87	1.60	14.32	1.54	3.9790	0.0002

TOTAL	68.28	5.89	75.37	6.08	5.1499	0.0001
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The above table show coping strategies used by the public and private sector bank managers. The above table show the comparison of coping strategies used among the managerial cadre of select public and private sector banking organizations. It shows that the total t-value is 5.1499. The various coping strategies followed by the managerial cadre in the select public and private sector banks were statistically significant

except the aspect of positive thinking (C2). The table further show that the t-value for escape / avoidance (C1) is statistically significant with the t-value of 9.8664 followed by problem solving (C3) with 3.9478. and social support (C4) with t-value of 3.9790. The above test results show that there exists a difference in the application of coping strategies by the managerial cadre in the public sector and private sector banking organizations.

Table No. 04
Symptom Management Strategies in Banking Sector

Coping Strategies	Public Sector Bank N=50		Private Sector Bank N=30		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Positive symptom management strategies (PSM) (M1)	20.48	1.81	25.36	1.94	11.3645	0.0001
Negative symptom management strategies (NSM) (M2)	13.65	1.05	11.81	1.22	7.1378	0.0001
TOTAL	34.13	2.86	36.17	3.16	4.4246	0.0001

The above table show employed on Symptom Management, two Symptom Management Strategies were extracted. These two Symptom Management Strategies were Positive symptom management strategies (PSM) (M1) and Negative symptom management strategies (NSM) (M2). The results of t-test indicated that the difference is significant at 0.05level of significance.

Table No.05
Coping Strategies among Male and Female Bank Managers in Public Sector

Coping Strategies	Male Public Sector Bank Managers N=45		Female Public Sector Bank Managers N=35		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Escape/Avoidance (E/A) (C1)	13.20	1.64	13.25	1.98	0.1235	0.9020
Positive Thinking (PT) (C2)	17.55	1.15	17.65	1.12	0.3902	0.6974
Problem Solving (PS) (C3)	15.20	1.39	15.22	1.27	0.0663	0.9473
Social Support (SS) (C4)	18.40	1.16	18.38	1.04	0.0800	0.9364
TOTAL	64.35	5.34	64.50	5.41	0.1239	0.9017

The above table show coping strategies used by the public sector bank Male and Female managers. The above table show the comparison of coping strategies used among the Male and Female managerial cadre of

public sector banking organizations. The various coping strategies followed by the Male and Female managerial cadre in the public sector bank were statistically not significant. The above test results show that

there exists a difference in the application of coping strategies by the Male and Female managerial cadre in the public sector banking organizations.

Table No. 06 , Coping Strategies among Male and Female Bank Managers in Private Sector

Coping Strategies	Male Private Sector Bank Managers N=45		Female Private Sector Bank Managers N=35		t-value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Escape/Avoidance (E/A) (C1)	15.38	1.24	15.50	1.38	0.4087	0.6839
Positive Thinking (PT) (C2)	17.26	1.73	17.09	1.65	0.4449	0.6577
Problem Solving (PS) (C3)	18.28	1.64	18.46	1.52	0.5027	0.6166
Social Support (SS) (C4)	16.44	1.82	16.54	1.94	0.2369	0.8134
TOTAL	67.36	6.43	67.59	6.49	0.1581	0.8748

The above table show coping strategies used by the private sector bank Male and Female managers. The above table show the comparison of coping strategies used among the Male and Female managerial cadre of private sector banking organizations. The various coping strategies followed by the Male and Female managerial cadre in the private sector bank were statistically not significant. The above test results show that there exists a difference in the application of coping strategies by the Male and Female managerial cadre in the private sector banking organizations.

Findings:-

1. The test results show that there is a significant difference in the level of stress among male and female cadres of the select banking organizations. Hence the alternate hypothesis (H1) is accepted. The major finding that emerges is that level of stress is higher among female bank managers as compare to male bank managers in both public and private sector banks but the difference was not significant.
2. The test revealed that Problem Solving Coping Strategies (C3) was used most frequently by the private sector bank managers.
3. The test results show that there exists a difference in the application of coping strategies by the managerial cadre in the public sector and private sector banking organizations.
4. The comparison of public sector and private sector results indicated that the extent of using coping strategies was higher in case of private sector as compare to public

sector .The difference is significant at 0.05 level of significance.

5. The results indicated that in case of private sector, Problem Solving and Coping Strategies (C3) are the difference was significant at 0.05 level of significance.
6. It shows that in case of private sector for Social Support Coping Strategies (C4) was higher as compare to the public sector and the difference is significant at 0.05 level of significance.
7. It shows that in case of private sector for Positive Thinking Coping Strategies (C2) was higher as compare to the public sector. The difference was not significant at any level.
8. The test revealed that Positive symptom management strategies (M1) were used most frequently by the public sector bank managers. This was followed by Negative symptom management strategies (M2).
9. The test revealed that Positive symptom management strategies (M1) were used most frequently by both the categories.
10. The results stated that in case of individual symptom management strategies extent of using both the strategies was higher in case of female bank managers but the difference was not significant at any level of significance.
11. The test results show that Coping strategies have a positive significant impact on the health of the managerial cadre in the banking organizations. Hence the alternate hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

Limitations Of The Study:-

1. The study is limited to only Ujjain district in Madhya Pradesh.

2. The study is limited to only 01 Public Sector and 01 Private Sector Banking Organizations. Hence the nature of stressors in the other public and private sector banks may differ with that of the selected sampling banks.

3. To investigate the physical health problems, only the most common health problems have been taken up for the study, while the respondents may be suffering from some other health problems which are not taken up in the study.

Conclusion:- The study concludes that female managerial cadre of the select banks are more vulnerable to stress and its multitude effects and they are subjected to more exposure towards a greater magnitude of work stress when compared to their male counterparts. The female managerial cadre felt overburdened with their work load due to their dual role performance as an employee and as well as a home maker and duties they had to discharge on both the platforms. The study concludes that the coping strategies like problem solving and social support have been found mostly used by the managerial cadre in the select banking organizations. Symptom management strategy was found to be utilized in both the ways of positive and negative dimensions. In order to reduce the job related stress, respondents were found to be using positive management symptom strategies more as compared to negative symptom management strategies. In order to achieve organizational efficiency, the banking organizations have to identify the potential reasons are causes of stress and the strategies of coping with the stress process.

Implications Of The Study:-

The research findings of the study provide a basic platform for Human resource policy reforms in order to combat stress and improve the health of the managerial cadre in the banking sector. The research findings of this study contributes both theoretically and pragmatically to the field of behavioural sciences and provides an insight into the identification of potential organizational stressors , measuring stress and coping strategies those the managerial cadre adapt to cope with the stress in the select public sector and private sector banking organizations.

Scope For Future Research:-

1. Descriptive research study can be made on the impact of stress on the productivity

levels of the banking employees working in public sector and private sector banking organizations.

2. Comparative research studies on the impact of stress can be made on the inter segment cadres among the working bank employees in both the public and private sector organizations.

3. Comparative research studies can be made on the role of stress and coping behavior on the organizational effectiveness of Indian and Foreign banks

4. Exploratory research study can be done on the influence of work culture on stress management practices in the banking industry.

5. Longitudinal research studies can be done conducted for detecting the relationship between stress and health among the banking professionals.

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